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SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF DEPENDENT PREPOSITIONS IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

**Gerok-Yerzhanova O.,
Podavets O.**

senior teachers

*Kostanay State Pedagogical Institute after U. Sultangazin
Tauelsizdik Street, 117*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7878431>

Abstract

This article touches upon the relevant issue in the learning process. The aspect of dependent prepositions in the English language requires special attention in terms of their meaning in the context. The attempt is made to define the major characteristics of dependent prepositions taking into consideration figurative meaning and its classification.

Keywords: metaphor; metonymy; subjectification; derived; compound; composite

To use English effectively, it is important to master four language skills, namely listening, speaking, reading and writing. Of all the four language skills, writing is considered the most difficult process. The majority of students encounter difficulties in using prepositions in terms of semantic aspects. As for the dependent prepositions, they affect the meaning of the words with which they are associated, often changing their meaning beyond recognition. Dependent prepositions have a function in the construction of a sentence. The origin of this type of speech comes from the roots of words of ancient origin.

All English prepositions can be divided into simple, compound, derived and composite. The *simple* type has an overwhelming number of prepositions. These include, for example, *against* (*with, on, to, under*), the prepositions *in* (*for, on, at*), *about*. *Compound* consists of several components. These include *where upon* (*after which, as a result of which*), *within* (*in, inside*). *Derived* ones come from words of other parts of speech. These include, for example, *concerning* (*about, by*).

Composite type uses phrases when forming. They consist of a word from another part of speech and one or two prepositions. These include, for example, *because of* (*due to, because of*), *with regard to* (*in relation to*). Any element from a compound preposition cannot

be shortened or expanded – it is a single whole unit. The meaning of *composite* is directly dependent on the significant word that is part of it. Mainly the composite prepositions can be referred to dependent ones as they acquire the specific characteristics in the context. Some linguists call them prepositions with the metaphorical meaning [1]. The only way to distinguish between the primary and abstract meaning is to memorise prepositions, which is a challenge for students to rise to. A pedagogical strategy is essential for students to pay attention to the cooccurrence, collocation, and discourse behaviour of prepositions.

The group of researchers classifies dependent prepositions according to their structural characteristics. By prepositional use, they mean collocations, patterns and idioms containing prepositions: a) preposition + noun: *at risk, on time, out of tune* b) noun + preposition: *overview of, absorption of, an increase in, lack of* c) adjective + preposition: *associated with, responsible for, interested in* d) verb + preposition: *worry about, suffer from, get rid of, die out* e) chunk containing preposition: *on my own, in the long run, in contact with, on the verge of, to the point of* f) idiom containing phrasal verb: *clear up your act, hang out, turn down* [2].

To demonstrate the semantic shift in meaning, the following examples are given:

1. As most young candidates for the pains and penalties of whaling stop at this same New Bedford, thence **to embark on** their voyage, it may as well be related that I, for one, had no idea of so doing. – Chapter 2, p. 31 [3]

2. I told him that I never liked to sleep two in a bed; that if I should ever do so, it would **depend upon** who the harpooner might be, ... – Chapter 3, p. 39 [3]

3. Again, I always go to sea as a sailor, because they make a **point of** paying me for my trouble, whereas they never pay passengers a single penny that I ever heard of. – Chapter 1, p. 28 [3]

4. I pay this particular compliment to Queequeg, because he **treated me with** so much civility and consideration, ... – Chapter 4, p. 57 [3]

5. He now took off his hat – a new beaver hat – when I came nigh singing out **with fresh surprise**. – Chapter 3, p. 49 [3]

6. Thinks I, Queequeg, **under the circumstances**, this is a very civilized overture; ... – Chapter 4, p. 57 [3]

Beitel, D. A., Raymond W. et al. present the classification of dependent prepositions according to the semantic changes. Thus, they identify the following pattern of semantic extension: *metaphor*, *metonymy*, and *subject*. Emphasizing the figurative meaning, they claim that figurative use is not arbitrary, though image schemata embodied through metonymic extension undefined incompatible these image schemata in various conceptual domains [4]. These are prepositions with metaphorical meanings - as a phrase with a verb, noun or adjective. It is dependent prepositions that cannot be replaced by other prepositions, since they are used to connect words in sentences or in certain phrases. Thus, the use of two prepositions is much more determined by the choice of adjacent words.

As far as metonymy is concerned, it occurs conceptually. The most frequent metonymic changes attested in the semantic changes of English prepositions involve conceptual continuity expressible as POSITION > DIRECTION > MOTION, whereby any of these concepts is part of a series of related concepts [5].

The concept of subjectification has been widely used to describe the phenomenon of grammatical shift.

This is an argumentative issue so far, whereas some linguists assume that there are human tendencies such as anthropocentrism and egocentricity that are involved in subjectification [6].

Taking into consideration the semantic domains of dependent prepositions and compiling the material of several investigations, we suggest the following classification of dependent prepositions with the focus on their semantic characteristics:

1. Metaphor (spatial – *under control*; temporal; grammatical/logical – *with surprise*)
2. Polysemy
3. Prototype (diachronically altered meaning)
4. Metonymy (contiguity in social physical or cultural experience; contiguity in the utterance; synecdoche) or (position – direction – motion)
5. Subjectification (emphasizing the speaker's attitude in a context)
6. Frame-of-Focus Variation (the aspect of space with the shift of focus)
7. Generalization

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